

METHODICAL APPROACHES IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Annotation: The development of a foreign language is always associated with the selection of relevant methods. The experience of teaching English by experts of this language is predominant. Its effective implementation and use in training programs, including federal ones, is one of the key issues of teaching English today.

Keywords: Methodical approaches, TBE technique, analysis of needs, class planning, traditional communicative and humanistic methods training, error correction, aspects of the language.

Introduction

Arguments concerning the benefits and drawbacks of using Russian and foreign techniques to teach English are still being debated today. In contemporary Russian education, the use of traditional methods has become the norm for proper conduct. Traditional language learning methods, according to many experts, are too monotonous in both their content and method of instruction. Each lesson starts with the development of grammar, moves on to vocabulary, and ends with repetitive exercises known as "Drills," which are meant to help students retain the material they have studied. Using traditional methods, the training course is deemed overly lengthy, which results in a high dropout rate [1-3].

Furthermore, it prevents one from being able to "plunge" into an English-speaking environment and get past the difficulty of internal translation. Even with fair criticism taken into consideration, the principal benefit of the conventional method—the gradual learning of core, basic knowledge intended for long-term assimilation and use—cannot be disputed. The popular and, in the view of the great majority of specialists, the most successful learning method is undoubtedly against this "archaic" approach: communication [4-9].

The main part

Its foundation is the aural perception of language; communication in the language is taught by conversation itself. Vibrant textbooks with workbooks and an

audio cassette set in English are also provided. This method cannot be referred to as universal, though, as it does not create a habit of speaking correctly, and the ability to communicate effectively is soon lost in a language-free environment. This straightforward study leads to the conclusion that is obvious: the best known techniques are used in a thorough and logical manner to produce the most effective and long-lasting outcome. The benefits of TBE as suggested by LTTC (London Pedagogical College) and the resources included in the Longman Teacher Development complex program will be discussed in this article [8-13].

This type of training course's promising approaches to teaching English are specifically designed to increase the amount of activity through the combination of different teaching philosophies, classroom management techniques, and the utilization of the newest resources for language study. It is indisputable that such an integrated approach is important. Under this approach, working with a student starts with a needs analysis using a variety of methods (completing the Menu-Approach testing, when the teacher offers programs that meet the needs and needs of the student; personal interview; work-shadowing-awareness and determination of ways overcoming the barriers that prevent the linguistic potential of the personality, including overcoming the language barrier).

In the end, a multifaceted strategy like this guarantees comprehensive data regarding the requirements of the learner and, if required, bolsters his desire, bringing the training process into correct alignment and figuring out what a specific learner has to do to reach the objective. This method suggests exploiting the successes of a suggestopedia (Suggestopaedia) [Suggestopedia, WWW] in the lack of appropriate motivation. It does this by building a particular educational process and fostering a favorable attitude toward it through the use of a suggestive methodology. After that, the instructor starts lesson planning, which is the process by which real materials—the "ingredients" for the lessons—are chosen [14-19].

First and foremost, these include newspapers, magazines, advertisements, papers, digital records, TV and radio shows, pamphlets, reports, the Internet, When learning place-specific prepositions, phrase structures, and word stress—basically everything that makes language learning easier and more varied while adhering to a particular language feature—Kewizener sticks out. In addition, the instructor chooses headings, tables, advice, and other resources that will be required during the session. The utilization of so much visual content guarantees the linkage of the visual

teaching approach, which facilitates a quicker memorization of vocabulary and grammar [17-20].

Furthermore, the methodology provides blends of the subsequent instructional strategies:

1. The communicative approach combined with a few conventional techniques when dictionaries were limited to Anglo-English. It is always necessary to study grammar and vocabulary in context.

2. The social and cultural context of the language being studied is one area in which the linguocultural teaching approach (Cultural Knowledge) is applicable. This "live" approach does not seek to master only "lifeless" lexical and grammatical structures, as 44% of errors are found inside the study and 52% are committed under the impact of the original language.

Given the significance of this, the question of how to develop "linguo-sociocultural competence," which enables one to appropriately "dissect" language under a cultural lens, emerges. However, the linguocultural approach only combines additional linguistic elements with the fundamentals of grammar and vocabulary—it does not remove them in the slightest. 3. According to Lieutenant, Gushchina, and WWW, the humanistic method is predicated on treating each pupil as an individual and providing examples of both introverted and extrovert conduct.

A personality-oriented approach is typically used in the educational plan, with the student serving as the "center" of the learning process.

The following kinds of activities in the class are the outcome of using an integrated approach to language learning: various gaming scenarios (roleplaying), collaborate with a partner, look for analogies, analogies for memory and reasoning, such as synonyms and antonyms (find synonyms \ opposites), figure out which claims are true or false (FALSE-True claims), Eliminate superfluous words, look for collective nouns in a group of words (Classical), present ideas, elucidate ideas, draw conclusions, include a country-study component by necessity, and practice creating a dialogue based on the suggested strategies. Fill in the blanks (GAP-Filling), Multiple Choice, Work with Word Formation, Transform (Paraphrasing) of statements, and identify and fix errors (Error Identification and Correction).

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